

ASSESSMENT OF SUSPECTED COVID-19 CHILDREN FOR PERCEIVED LEVELS OF STRESS, ANXIETY AND DEPRESSION DURING COVID19 OUTBREAK IN A TERTIARY CENTRE – AN ONLINE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND- Children and teenagers who live in regions that are prone to natural disasters or man-made catastrophes, such as epidemics, need to have access to public health programmes that will teach them how to be resilient in the face of adversity of all sizes. It is therefore absolutely necessary to screen children who are brought for any kind of medical attention, especially the screening, sample collection, admission, or even post discharge, for any kind of emotional or behavioural disturbances, and to identify early signs of anxiety or depression, if there are any, and to address their issues, in order to ensure their mental wellbeing and to optimise the effectiveness of the medical treatment for the best possible way to maintain the child's overall health.

Hence, we performed this study to assess the early markers of stress, anxiety and depression in children admitted as Covid-19 suspects.

Objective : to assess perceived levels of stress, anxiety and depression among children during covid19.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This prospective observational study included patients of pediatric age group admitted in Bowring and Lady Curzon Hospital as Covid-19 suspects during the second wave, meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria were chosen randomly, which included 30 subjects. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Ethics committee of Medical College to carry out the study. A semi structured interview schedule was prepared by the researcher to understand the various socio demographic characteristics of the respondents, Child Behaviour Checklist (CBCL) and Children's Revised Impact of Event Scale (CRIES-13) was used.

Results

The scores on the CRIES-13 test were found to be considerably higher for children who came from households that had been divorced ($p = 0.047$) and for children who came from families with incomes of less than \$2,500 ($p = 0.031$).

When the CBCL was given to the parents, the following CBCL scales showed significant increases in their average scores: anxiety/depression ($p = 0.021$), social issues ($p = 0.041$), and aggressive problems ($p = 0.0321$).

CONCLUSION

In this study, we observed that during the COVID19 pandemic lock-down, children suffered from moderate amount of stress, depression and PTSD. Hence, we should counsel such children in vulnerable families in order to prevent such occurrence in the future.

INTRODUCTION

What began in December 2019 in Wuhan, China as a cluster of pneumonia cases presenting with symptoms ranging from fever, cough, cold, rapid breathing, and abdominal discomfort to severe acute respiratory distress was found to be caused by a novel corona virus. The virus was confirmed as the culprit. In January of 2020, it was announced that an outbreak of this viral phenomenon was occurring in Wuhan, China. As of right now, there are over 3 million persons affected, and they are located in more than 200 different nations. There have already been over 2 lakh fatalities reported in various parts of the world up to this point. The spectrum of the disease ranges from the absence of any symptoms to a severe acute respiratory illness that requires the assistance of mechanical devices.^[1] It is still not quite apparent what precipitated the appearance of the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2), but those events certainly played a role. It has been discovered that the virus transmitted through surface contact. As a result of the World Health Organization's (WHO) declaration that COVID 19 is a pandemic various governments have issued orders for 'lockdowns' and called for social distancing and other personal protection measures in an effort to halt or postpone the rate of the disease's spread.^[2]

In children, the symptoms of Covid-19 are said to be less severe than in adults, and the risk of death appears to be low. At the time this article was being written, the state of Kerala was where it was stated that India's last child had passed away. Children account for one percent to five percent of the cases that have been confirmed by the laboratory.^[3]

It should come as no surprise that the most important threat to the health of children around the world posed by the virus is not likely to be caused by Covid-19 in children; rather, it will most likely be the socioeconomic repercussions of the pandemic's protracted duration. From the 21st of March until the 3rd of May in the year 2020, India is under lockdown. Children are not unaffected by the grave consequences of the influenza pandemic that has been going on. Children's mental health and wellness will undoubtedly suffer as a result of the stress brought on by worries, unanswered questions, physical and social isolation, schools being closed for extended periods of time, and the disruption of normal daily life, on both the social and economic fronts. Whenever they are confronted with the unexpected and the unknown, children often exhibit a variety of stress reactions. Due to their precarious situation, this population should be given significant attention.^[4]

Children and teenagers who live in regions that are prone to natural disasters or man-made catastrophes, such as epidemics, need to have access to public health programmes that will teach them how to be resilient in the face of adversity of all sizes, from the most insignificant setbacks to the most catastrophic events in their lives. Children and adolescents are able to readily overcome a situation of distress and prospectively stabilise emotionally and physiologically if they are supported effectively and correctly by healthcare experts, families, and other social ties, including the school environment. ^[5-6]

It is therefore absolutely necessary to screen children who are brought for any kind of medical attention, especially the screening, sample collection, admission, or even post discharge, for any kind of emotional or behavioural disturbances, and to identify early signs of anxiety or depression, if there are any, and to address their issues, in order to ensure their mental wellbeing and to optimise the effectiveness of the medical treatment for the best possible way to maintain the child's overall health.

The most significant functional reasons of disability in childhood are those related to the child's emotions and behavior. There is a significant incidence of behavioral issues among preschool-aged children. According to a number of studies, severe behavioral issues are present in 7% of children between the ages of three and four. Many studies have also demonstrated that behavior problems remain consistent throughout the course of time. ^[7-10]

Because the COVID-19 pandemic can have a negative impact on mental health, this study was carried out to determine the prevalence of psychological stress in young Indian people during the crisis time. Hence, we performed this study to assess the early markers of stress, anxiety and depression in children admitted as Covid-19 suspects.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This prospective observational study included patients of pediatric age group admitted in Bowring and Lady Curzon Hospital as Covid-19 suspects during its second wave from April 2021 to June 2021, those meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected by simple random sampling, which included 30 subjects. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Ethics committee of Medical College to carry out the study (BMCRI/PS/09/2020-21). This study

attracts no monetary compensation. The outcome of the study will be used to help health care professionals involved.

Tools for Data Collection

1.) A semi structured interview schedule was prepared by the researcher to understand the various socio demographic characteristics of the respondents.

2.) Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL)

It is a parent report form to screen for emotional, behavioral, and social problems. Separate checklist is available for 1.5-5yrs and 6-18yrs. Questions are associated with problems on a syndrome scale in eight different categories: anxious/depressed, withdrawn/depressed, somatic complaints, social problems, thought problems, attention problems, rule breaking behavior and aggressive behavior.^[10]

4.) The Children's Revised Impact of Event Scale (CRIES 13) :

Developed by Horowitz et al^[11] to experience the main phenomenon of re-experiencing the traumatic event and of avoidance of that event and the feelings to which it gave rise.

There are 8 items that are scored on a four point scale

- Not at all – 0
- Rarely -1
- Sometimes – 3
- Often – 5

And three subscales

- Intrusion = sum of the items 1+4+8+9
- Avoidance = sum of the items 2+6+&+10
- Arousal = sum of items 3+5+11+12+13 (Annexure 3)

Procedure for data collection

This was a follow up study conducted during COVID 19 second wave from April 2021 to June 2021 in the state of Karnataka in India. The data was collected online through the questionnaires mentioned above. From the educated parents who understood English and gave their informed consent were approached orally from phone before proceeding with the study. The questionnaire consisted of demographics and CREIS-13 and CBCL questions to assess the stress, anxiety, and depression levels. Demographic variables included name, age, contact no. address, gender, occupation /class.

The questionnaire was shared online either via WhatsApp or other means. The questionnaire was in English language. The questions were multiple choice type with 1 best response and few yes or no questions. At the end of the questionnaire feedback/suggestions were taken from respondents. Each correct answer 1 score, wrong answer no score. In the event the patient did not own a smart phone, he was interviewed over the telephone and the responses were collected.

Those who were screened were contacted again on 14th day and 28th day for reassessment of physical and mental health over the phone by using similar the questionnaire.

Statistical Analysis

The data collected will be analyzed statistically using descriptive statistics namely mean, standard deviation, percentage wherever applicable. Student's T test, Chi square test and Pearson's correlation will be used where deemed necessary. A p value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

More over two-thirds of the students were girls (64.39%), whereas only 35.61% of the students were male. 78.72%, were between the ages of 10 and 15. In addition, around 62.32% of respondents acknowledged that their family belongs to the lower middle class economically. While boys only reported modest levels of stress and anxiety, girls reported significant levels of stress and severe levels of anxiety. Both boys and girls reported experiencing moderate levels of depression.

20.9% of the children in the study scored a score lower than 30 points on the CRIES-13, which resulted in a mean score of 16.43 12.57 (min-max: 0–65). The results of the CRIES-13 showed that there was no variation in the scores based on the gender of the children. The scores on the CRIES-13 test were found to be considerably higher for children who came from households that had been divorced ($p = 0.047$) and for children who came from families with incomes of less than \$2,500 ($p = 0.031$).

When the CBCL was given to the parents, the following CBCL scales showed significant increases in their average scores: anxiety/depression ($p = 0.021$), social issues ($p = 0.041$), and aggressive problems ($p = 0.0321$).

DISCUSSION

Our research indicated that there was a significant psychological impact on children who were suspected of COVID 19. The results of the CBCL were analyzed, and the findings revealed that throughout the lockdown period, both internalizing and externalizing symptoms became more severe across the board in the sample. This conclusion is in line with what has been found in the previous research. Similar results were seen by Fassi et al.,^[12] the CBCL of 141 participants under the age of 18 who were diagnosed with Neurologic and Psychiatric illnesses were compared, and throughout the lockdown period, a worsening in emotional and behavioral difficulties was observed. Because these children have a harder time adjusting to new environments, it is plausible that being confined to the house and having their daily routines disrupted contributes to their emotional and behavioral difficulties.

It was discovered that the CRIES-13 scores of families with incomes of less than \$2,500 were considerably higher than average. This outcome provided evidence in favor of our hypothesis. It is well established that persons who have a low socioeconomic status are more likely to suffer from anxiety and depression.^[13-18] According to the findings of a study carried out by Melchoir and colleagues, a significantly higher percentage of young people from households with a lower socioeconomic level suffered from anxiety and depression, and these individuals had a more fragile mental state. However, the results of the study showed that the largest link was with parental income.^[19] This is despite the fact that factors such as the divorce of parents and parental psychopathology have an effect on the mental health of young people. Similarly is one

of the few studies that has established that such socioeconomic inequalities are associated to anxiety in children and adolescents.^[20] Although it is known that socioeconomic factors affect depression and anxiety symptoms in young people, this study is one of the few studies that has demonstrated this connection.

The results of the CRIES-13 showed that the children who came from broken families had much higher average scores. Children may have a difficult time adjusting to the changes in their social and financial environments that are brought about by a divorce.^[21] It is well recognized that children who have been exposed to prolonged stress and traumatic situations while still infants or young children have a greater risk of developing mental health problems. Children who come from homes that have gone through a divorce have been found to have a heightened sensitivity to anxiety.^[22-23] This heightened sensitivity to anxiety has been linked to an increased risk of developing mental health conditions such as panic disorder, agoraphobia, post-traumatic stress disorder, major depressive disorder, social anxiety, and drug misuse. In line with previous research studies, we too found that children who come from broken homes had a significantly increased chance of having post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).^[24-26]

Strength and limitations of this study

The results of this study cannot be used to establish causal links mainly due to the lower sample size. While gathering online responses can save time, the accuracy of the data cannot be guaranteed. Because of this, conclusions drawn from this study cannot be applied to the whole population.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we observed that during the COVID19 pandemic lock-down, children suffered from moderate amount of stress, depression and PTSD. Hence, we should counsel such children in vulnerable families in order to prevent such occurrence in the future.

REFERENCES

1. Holshue ML, DeBolt C, Lindquist S, Lofy KH, Wiesman J, Bruce H, et al. First Case of 2019 Novel Coronavirus in the United States. *N Engl J Med*. 2020;382(10):929-36.
2. WHO. Covid19 Pandemic 2020 [Available from: <https://www.who.int/dg/speeches/detail/who-director-general-s-opening-remarks-at-the-media-briefing-on-covid-19---11-march-2020>].
3. Ludvigsson JF. Systematic review of COVID-19 in children show milder cases and a better prognosis than adults. *Acta Paediatr*. 2020 Mar 23.
4. Zimmermann P, Curtis N. Coronavirus Infections in Children Including COVID-19. *PIDJ*. 2020 Mar 12.
5. Liu S, Yang L, Zhang C, Xiang YT, Liu Z, Hu S, et al. Online mental health services in China during the COVID-19 outbreak. *Lancet Psychiatry*. 2020;7(4):e17–8.
6. Pfefferbaum B, North CS. Mental health and the Covid-19 pandemic. *N Engl J Med*. 2020;383:510–2.
7. Radwan A, Radwan E. Social and Economic Impact of School Closure during the Outbreak of the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Quick Online Survey in the Gaza Strip. *Pedagogical Res*. 2020; 5(4): em0068. <https://doi.org/10.29333/pr/8254>
8. Bakioğlu F, Korkmaz O, Ercan H. Fear of COVID-19 and positivity: mediating role of intolerance of uncertainty, depression, anxiety, and stress. *Int J Mental Health Addict*. 2020:
9. Rehman U, Shahnawaz MG, Khan NH, Kharshiing KD, Khursheed M, Gupta K, et al. Depression, anxiety and stress among Indians in times of Covid-19 lockdown. *Community Ment Health J*. 2021;57(1):42–8.

10. Achenbach TM, Edelbrock C. The child behavior profile: II. Boys aged 12-16 and girls aged 6-11 and 12-16. *J Consult Clin Psychol* 1979; 47:223-33.
11. Horowitz, M. J., Wilner, N., and Alvarez, W. (1979). Impact of event scale: A measure of subjective stress. *Psychosom. Med.*, 41, 209-218
12. Fazzi E., Galli J. New clinical needs and strategies for care in children with neurodisability during COVID-19. *Dev. Med. Child Neurol.* 2020;62:879–880. doi: 10.1111/dmcn.14557.
13. Zhang Y, Ma ZF. Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Mental Health and Quality of Life among Local Residents in Liaoning Province, China: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health.* 2020;17:2381.
14. Reilly C., Muggeridge A., Cross J.H. The perceived impact of COVID-19 and associated restrictions on young people with epilepsy in the UK: Young people and caregiver survey. *Seizure.* 2021;85:111–114.
15. Wanigasinghe J, Jayawickrama A, Hewawitharana G, Munasinghe J, Weeraratne CT, Ratnayake P, et al., Experience during COVID-19 lockdown and self-managing strategies among caregivers of children with epilepsy: A study from low middleincome country. *Seizure.* 2021;84:112–115.
16. Bailey T, Hastings RP, Totsika V. COVID-19 impact on psychological outcomes of parents, siblings and children with intellectual disability: Longitudinal before and during lockdown design. *J Intellect Disabil Res* 2021;65:397–404.
17. Alhuzimi T. Stress and emotional wellbeing of parents due to change in routine for children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) at home during COVID-19 pandemic in Saudi Arabia. *Res Dev Disabil.* 2021;108:103822.
18. Wittchen HU, Zhao S, Kessler RC, Eaton WW. DSM-III-R Generalized Anxiety Disorder in the National Comorbidity Survey. *Arch Gen Psychiatry.* 1994;51:355–364.
19. Melchior M, Chastang JF, Walburg V, Arseneault L, Galéra C, Fombonne E. Family income and youths' symptoms of depression and anxiety: a longitudinal study of the French GAZEL Youth cohort. *Depress Anxiety.* 2010;27:1095–1103.
20. Costello EJ, Compton SN, Keeler G, Angold A. Relationships between poverty and psychopathology: a natural experiment. *JAMA.* 2003;290:2023–2029.

21. Amone-P'Olak K, Burger H, Ormel J, Huisman M, Verhulst FC, Oldehinkel AJ. Socioeconomic position and mental health problems in pre and early-adolescents: The trails study. *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol.* 2009;44:231–238.
22. Muntaner C, Eaton WW, Miech R, O'Campo P. Socioeconomic position and major mental disorders. *Epidemiol Rev.* 2004;26:53–62.
23. Vezzetti VC. New approaches to divorce with children: a problem of public health. *Heal Psychol Open.* 2016;3:2055102916678105. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
24. Theis N, Campbell N, De Leeuw J, Owen M, Schenke KC. The effects of COVID-19 restrictions on physical activity and mental health of children and young adults with physical and/or intellectual disabilities. *Disabil Health J.* 2021;14:101064.
25. Raffagnato A, Iannattone S, Tascini B, Venchiarutti M, Broggio A, Zanato S, et al.,. The COVID-19 Pandemic: A Longitudinal Study on the Emotional-Behavioral Sequelae for Children and Adolescents with Neuropsychiatric Disorders and Their Families. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021;18:9880. doi: 10.3390/ijerph18189880.
26. Operto FF, Pastorino GM, Pippa F, Padovano C, Vivenzio V, Scuoppo C, et al.,. Psychiatric Symptoms and Parental Stress in Children and Adolescents With Epilepsy. *Front Neurol.* 2021;12:778410. doi: 10.3389/fneur.2021.778410.